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CLINICAL METHOD FOR THE RESTORATION OF DAMAGED NON-REMOVABLE METAL-PLASTIC PROSTHETIC SPLINTS

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the options for non-removable splinting using orthopedic structures for periodontal disease. The characteristics of tires, their advantages and disadvantages are given. The problems of periodontology in terms of overloading the abutment teeth with orthopedic structures and the moments of solving this with the help of orthopedic metal-plastic splints and removable dentures are outlined, and the clinical methodology for repairing (restoration) of damaged metal-plastic splints-prostheses is described in detail.

Keywords: periodontitis, tires, metal-plastic construction.

The use of splinting at the first signs of pathological tooth mobility is an integral component of the orthopedic treatment of this pathology [1]. All these are mainly manifestations of localized or generalized periodontitis [2], one of the serious diseases of the dentition. For fixed splinting, both stamped crowns and solid structures are used [5]. There are splinting structures using Polyglas tape [3, 4]. Stamped structures carry with them the absence of a cosmetic component, which is currently unacceptable. Purely cast crowns require hard tooth preparation and are very heavy, which does not contribute to effective complex orthopedic treatment of periodontitis. Metal-ceramic and metal-plastic-mass splinting structures have proven themselves better. They are much lighter than non-combined one-piece cast structures. Constructions made of cermet have proven themselves aesthetically well. But, taking into account the properties of cermets, with an antagonizing moment, "hard hits" are obtained. This does not help to alleviate the "provoked" periodontium. A metal-plastic construction is one of the few successful designs for aesthetic periodontal treatment by splinting. These structures are not heavy, and although the plastic has the ability to absorb oral fluid over time, they have a

softer contact antagonizing threshold, which is beneficial for the periodontium in the stabilization stage. Very often, with a fixed bite height in the frontal area and the absence of antagonistic teeth in lateral with orthognathic bite, the frame of the metal-plastic prosthesis on the lower jaw is exposed. This is due to the fact that patients refuse to use a removable prosthesis, and implantation in this case is not indicated or is too financially burdensome for the patient.

At the same time, the provoked periodontium receives an additional load, holding the full power of the dentoalveolar system. Usually, in this case, it is recommended to remove the metal-plastic prosthesis and make a new one, followed by unloading the dentition and manufacturing a removable structure. Removing the prosthesis is a laborious procedure, and re-manufacturing is expensive for the patient and does not spare the load on the periodontium. We offer a method for clinical restoration of the structure without it cutting (removal). We recommend doing this as follows. With the help of the silicone mass, we obtain an impression for the working model, and with the help of the alginate mass, for the auxiliary one. After that, the resulting models are plastered in an occluder, and the height of

the central occlusion determined in the clinic is fixed. The lost height of the crowns is modeled on the model with wax. They are brought into contact with the antagonist teeth, and the model is duplicated. A silicone combined impression is taken from the duplicated model. Further, in the clinic, a metal-plastic structure to be restored in the oral cavity is treated with honey, dried, treated with a monomer, freeing from self-hardening plastic, after which the color of the plastic is determined. Synma-M plastic powder of a given color is mixed with a monomer, freeing it from self-hardening plastic, and filling it with areas that require restoration in the print. After that, the impression is set in place in the oral cavity. After waiting 7–10 minutes, the spoon is removed from the impression and deforming the impression, the metal-plastic crowns restored with plastic are released, after which they are processed, ground and polished in the oral cavity. The patient is given recommendations on the care of metal-plastic crowns. Four patients with this pathology were observed in the clinic over a 2-year period. A delayed examination of each of them was carried out. At a repeated visual examination after six months, the boundary between the new and old plastic was not determined, there were no color changes and breaks, no chips. Based on this, we recommend using this technique in typical cases when using splint

structures in orthopedic treatment of periodontal diseases. In this case, when restoring the structure, a sparing attitude towards the periodontium and the financial situation of the patient is determined.

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PHONETIC PARTICIPATION OF THE PATIENT IN THE MANUFACTURE OF COMPLETE REMOVABLE LAMELLAR DENTURES

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ABSTRACT

Active phonetic participation of the patient in the manufacture of prostheses at the stage of checking the setting of artificial teeth on a solid basis and the use of an entropy assessment of the pronunciation of a consonant sound contributes to faster speech adaptation to prostheses in the process of their manufacture.

Keywords: complete removable denture, use of phonetics.

To restore high-quality speech function during orthopedic treatment with complete removable laminar prostheses, special importance must be attached to the design of artificial dentitions of a particularly frontal group. Many authors recommend designing artificial dentition in such a way as to reproduce the signs of the chewing apparatus as much as possible. According to a number of researchers [1, 2], ideal occlusal relationships are a theoretical model that is not a biological reality or necessity. When designing artificial dentitions, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the status and individual characteristics of the masticatory apparatus of a patient with a complete absence of

teeth at the time of treatment, anatomical, topographical and functional landmarks. To create sagittal and transversal curves in complete removable lamellar dentures, M.E. Vasiliev, based on the anatomical rules for placing artificial teeth, proposed to design artificial dentitions relative to the glass plane [3]. A number of authors [4] point out that this technique does not always provide good aesthetic and phonetic results, since the frontal groups of artificial teeth of the upper and lower jaws are designed with average anatomical principles and do not always correspond to individual pronunciation features in hard bases. of the oral cavity at the clinical stage of manufacturing a full-removable lamellar prosthesis, during which individual occlusal surfaces